

Innovative Approaches to Monitoring CPD Engagement for HIV Education: Insights from Digital Medical CPD Platform

Abstract

Objective: This study evaluates the engagement and outcomes of a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) activity titled "*Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations*", hosted on a digital medical platform. The aim was to highlight the effectiveness of data-driven monitoring techniques in enhancing education and supporting healthcare professionals (HCPs) in managing people living with HIV (PLWHIV).

Methods: Data was collected using Mixpanel to track user engagement, completion rates, and demographic trends. The analysis focused on participant roles, provincial engagement patterns, and CPD ranking among other platform offerings. Metrics were further contextualised against national HIV prevalence data and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets.

Results: A total of 4,359 HCPs successfully completed the CPD activity, representing 8.7% of the platform's active users. Emergency medicine personnel accounted for the largest share of completions (51.3%), followed by general practitioners (64% of the doctor cohort). Provincial engagement varied significantly, with Gauteng leading at 59% of completions, followed by KwaZulu-Natal (24.3%) and Western Cape (16.7%). The CPD ranked fifth among all platform offerings, highlighting strong interest in HIV-related education.

Conclusions: This CPD activity demonstrates the impact of community-driven and data-informed approaches in scaling education for HCPs. Provincial variations in engagement align with regional HIV prevalence, emphasising the need for tailored strategies to address healthcare priorities. The findings underscore the value of digital platforms in supporting SDG 3 by fostering professional development and strengthening health systems through innovative monitoring and evaluation techniques.

Keywords: HIV education, Continuing Professional Development, healthcare professionals, data-informed monitoring, Sustainable Development Goals, digital platforms, provincial engagement

Introduction

The Role of Continuing Professional Development in Healthcare Delivery for HIV Management and Prevention

Continuing professional development (CPD) serves as a cornerstone for maintaining and enhancing the competencies of healthcare professionals (HCPs). In the context of HIV management and prevention, CPD is vital to equipping HCPs with up-to-date knowledge, skills, and evidence-based practices. The dynamic landscape of HIV care, characterised by rapid advancements in treatment options, prevention strategies, and clinical guidelines, necessitates ongoing education to ensure optimal patient outcomes. By participating in CPD activities, HCPs can improve their capacity to deliver comprehensive, high-quality care, thereby contributing to broader public health goals such as reducing new HIV infections and improving the quality of life for individuals living with HIV.

Enhancing Impact Through Monitoring and Evaluation of CPD Activities

Effective monitoring and evaluation of CPD activities play a critical role in assessing their relevance, reach, and impact on healthcare delivery. By systematically collecting and analysing data on HCP engagement, completion rates, and knowledge acquisition, CPD providers can identify gaps and opportunities for improvement. Furthermore, these insights enable the tailoring of educational content to better address the specific needs of healthcare professionals and the communities they serve.

In support of this, Gallegos P.J. et al. found that online CPD training was as effective as in-person training, highlighting the potential of digital platforms to deliver impactful education at scale¹. By leveraging such findings, CPD programmes can enhance their design and implementation, ensuring they meet the evolving needs of healthcare professionals in diverse settings.

In the context of the global HIV response, innovative approaches to monitoring and evaluation have the potential to strengthen health systems and programmes. Tracking metrics such as user participation, participant professional roles, and engagement in educational modules can provide valuable feedback on the effectiveness of CPD initiatives. This data-driven approach not only enhances the quality of CPD activities but also aligns with broader goals, such as achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages. By leveraging insights from monitoring and evaluation, CPD programmes can play a pivotal role in advancing HIV education and prevention efforts².

Objective

The aim of this study is to evaluate the engagement and outcomes of a CPD activity focused on HIV, hosted on an online health platform, and to demonstrate its role in enhancing education and strengthening healthcare systems. By examining user engagement metrics, completion rates, and the overall impact of the activity, this research seeks to highlight the effectiveness of CPD initiatives in addressing educational gaps and supporting healthcare professionals in the fight against HIV.

Methods

Data Collection and Metrics

The data for this study was collected using Mixpanel, a powerful analytics platform designed to track user interactions with digital content and provide actionable insights. Mixpanel allows for detailed tracking of user behaviours, such as engagement patterns, completion rates, and time spent on specific activities. This information was used to generate a comprehensive understanding of how healthcare professionals interacted with the CPD content.

The metrics analysed include:

- **Completion Rates:** Total number of users who completed the CPD activity.
- **Participant Professional Role:** Categorisation of users by professional roles, such as pre-hospital care providers, doctors, and allied health professionals.
- **CPD Ranking:** Ranking of CPD compared to others on the platform
- **Engagement Metrics:** Data on the demographics of where the HCPs completing the CPD are practising. This included geographic regions to identify patterns in participation across different provinces and the potential correlation with regional healthcare needs.

To further analyse the data, graphs and percentage calculations were performed using Google Sheets (Excel). These visualisations and summaries provided clear insights into trends and patterns. While this analysis is provisional, pending confirmation with the data analyst, it serves as a foundational approach for interpreting the data and drawing meaningful conclusions about the CPD activity's effectiveness.

Inclusion criteria

Data was included in the study if:

- The professional role is clearly defined
- Healthcare professional has been verified to be registered with their respective council for example HPCSA registration for doctors, nurses and other allied health professionals or SAPC registration for pharmacists
- The HCP passed the CPD activity titled 'Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations'

Exclusion criteria

Of the HCPs that participated in the CPD and passed the following were professional roles were excluded

- Excluded if professional role is not clearly defined i.e 'undefined'

- CPD submissions that were not passed as the HCP would have an opportunity to try again, only if they have a successfully passed the CPD activity that it blocks out resubmission

Ethics approval

Ethics approval for this study was granted by Prof. Irhuma, Head of Clinical Governance at the company providing the data. Approval was provided with the understanding that the data used for the study would remain aggregated and anonymised, ensuring that no participant or sponsor could be identified. The CPD content and outcomes were not linked to any commercial interests in the abstract or related research outputs.

Results

Completion Rates and Participant Professional Roles

Figure 1: Total CPD completions amongst healthcare professionals who participated in activity

The CPD activity recorded a total of 4359 completions. A total of 2237 HCPs classified as pre-hospital i.e emergency medicine personnel, such as paramedics, completed the CPD activity. Doctors made 1575 out of the 4359 (36%) of all passed CPD completions. 100 pharmacists completed the CPD, accounting for about 2.3% of participants. 48 (1.1%) of passed

CPD completions were from dentists. A relatively low number of nurses participated, with 55 completions, making up about 1.3% of the total.

Figure 2: Doctor Segment Analysis

Of the 1575 that completed and passed the CPD activity the largest cohort were general practice (GP) doctors at 64%. 17.4% of the doctors were Community Service doctors. 78 (5%) were specialist doctors. 13.5% were medical officers.

CPD Ranking

Figure 3: CPD Ranking - As compared to all CPDs on platform

Ranked no. 5 of CPDs that recorded the most passed completions

The CPD 'Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations' ranked as number five of the most passed completions between July 2024 - January 2025.

Engagement Metrics

Figure 4.1: Analysis of 'Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations' CPD participation in 3 of the most engaged provinces in South Africa

Figure 4.2: Analysis of 'All Other CPD' participation in 3 of the most engaged provinces in South Africa

Engagement by Province:

The engagement with the "Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations" CPD (HIV-CPD) varied across provinces, showcasing notable trends:

- **HIV-CPD Engagement:**
 - Gauteng recorded the highest participation, with 59% of successful completions.
 - KwaZulu-Natal followed with 24.3% of completions
 - Western Cape accounted for 16.7%, indicative of relatively lower engagement in this region compared to Gauteng and KwaZulu-Natal.
- **Overall CPD Engagement (Excluding HIV-CPD):**
 - Gauteng remained the leading province, with 57.3% of successful completions, emphasising its position as a hub for healthcare services and education.
 - Western Cape showed a higher share at 22.3%, reflecting strong interest in CPD activities within this province.
 - KwaZulu-Natal accounted for 20.4%, underscoring its significant but slightly lower participation compared to Western Cape.

Discussion

CPD Completion

The HIV-CPD was successfully completed by 4,359 healthcare professionals (HCPs). With approximately 50,000 active users on the medical health platform, this represents 8.7% of eligible HCPs who participated and successfully completed the activity. While this proportion highlights significant engagement, it also points to opportunities for increasing outreach and participation in future CPD activities. Ensuring that more HCPs access and complete CPD activities is essential for maximising their impact on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

Participant Professional Roles

Interestingly, HCPs categorised as 'pre-medicine,' representing those in emergency medicine such as paramedics, accounted for 51.3% of the successful HIV-CPD completions. This significant representation underscores the critical role of paramedics in the continuum of HIV care, particularly in managing emergency situations where HIV exposure may occur. Chaudhary R. et al. emphasised the importance of educating medical workers, including paramedic staff, on diseases such as Hepatitis B, C, and HIV to prevent fatal situations³. This aligns with the observed trend, suggesting that emergency medicine personnel recognise the value of up-to-date HIV knowledge in enhancing their clinical decision-making and preparedness. Further emphasis on tailoring CPD activities to meet the needs of this group may enhance both participation and the broader impact of such programmes.

Doctors constituted the second largest group of participants, with 1,575 completions, representing 36.1% of the total. As frontline providers of patient care, it is imperative for doctors to remain informed about advancements in medications, treatment protocols, and guidelines to

ensure the highest standard of patient care. Their strong representation in the CPD activity reflects a recognition of the critical role of continuous learning in maintaining clinical excellence.

Participation from other HCP segments was comparatively lower, with allied health professionals accounting for 4%, clinical associates 3.7%, pharmacists 2.3%, nurses 1.3%, and dentists 1.1%. These figures highlight the need for broader awareness and targeted outreach to encourage greater participation among these groups. Increased involvement, particularly among nurses, is anticipated in the future as the South African Nursing Council (SANC) begins implementing CPD participation as a competency requirement. Given that nurses often serve as the first point of contact in primary healthcare settings, their participation in CPD activities focused on HIV is essential for equipping them with the latest knowledge and skills. This is especially crucial as they play a pivotal role in patient triage, education, and initial management before cases are escalated to doctors. Enhanced efforts to engage these underrepresented groups will be critical for ensuring a comprehensive and well-prepared healthcare workforce.

Doctor Segment Analysis

General practitioners (GPs) accounted for 64% of the doctor segment's completions, highlighting their dominant presence in South Africa's medical community. As the largest group of doctors in the country, GPs are often the first point of contact for patients, making their engagement with up-to-date HIV management strategies vital for improving clinical outcomes⁴. Their participation underscores the importance of ensuring that frontline doctors have access to the latest innovations in HIV care.

Community service doctors made up 17.4% of the doctor segment's completions. This strong representation is notable, as community service doctors typically account for only 5–10% of the medical practitioner workforce in a given year⁴. Their engagement reflects a promising trend among early-career doctors recognising the importance of HIV education in their practice. This level of participation also suggests that digital CPD formats resonate well with this group, offering flexible learning opportunities amidst their demanding schedules.

Medical officers and specialists accounted for 13.5% and 5% of the doctor segment's completions, respectively. The involvement of specialists indicates that HIV education remains relevant across diverse professional roles within the medical field, reinforcing the need for inclusive CPD content tailored to various levels of expertise.

Challenges and Opportunities in CPD Participation

While the participation among doctors is commendable, there remain challenges such as time constraints due to heavy workloads, limited access to CPD content, and competing professional priorities^{5,6}. Online CPD activities, such as the HIV-CPD, address these barriers by providing on-demand access to high-quality educational material. This flexibility allows doctors to engage with the content at their convenience, whether via mobile devices or computers, unlike fixed-time physical webinars which may limit reach and accessibility. Expanding such digital

CPD offerings could significantly enhance participation rates and impact across all healthcare professional groups^{5,6}.

CPD Ranking

The HIV-CPD was ranked as the 5th most completed CPD on the online platform between July 2024 and January 2025. This ranking demonstrates the strong interest and demand for HIV-focused education among healthcare professionals. The consistent engagement highlights the relevance of the content and the recognition of its importance in improving clinical practices related to HIV care.

This ranking also underscores the competitive nature of CPD offerings on the platform, where numerous activities vie for attention. Achieving a top-five position amidst diverse educational modules indicates that HIV-CPD has successfully resonated with its target audience. The achievement reinforces the need to continuously update and promote similar CPD activities to sustain interest and engagement among healthcare professionals.

Engagement Metrics – Provincial Considerations

Analysis of Participation in Major Provinces

Analysis of participation in the "Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations" CPD highlights engagement trends in three of South Africa's most engaged provinces: Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), and the Western Cape.

According to UNAIDS (2023), approximately 7.7 million people in South Africa are living with HIV, with a national prevalence of 13.9%⁷. These statistics highlight the critical need for effective HIV education to equip healthcare professionals to manage this significant health challenge.

Gauteng: Gauteng accounted for 59% of the CPD completions, making it the leading province in participation. This is likely due to Gauteng's status as a hub for healthcare services, with a high concentration of healthcare professionals and greater access to digital resources. The province's 2019 HIV prevalence (13.05%) aligns closely with the national average, underscoring the importance of consistent engagement in HIV-related CPD activities to maintain high standards of patient care⁸.

KwaZulu-Natal: KZN recorded 24.3% of the CPD completions, less than half of Gauteng's participation. However, KZN's 2019 HIV prevalence stands at 18.23%, significantly higher than the national average⁸. This discrepancy suggests an urgent need to increase CPD engagement among HCPs in this province to address the high burden of HIV and ensure that healthcare providers are well-prepared to meet patient needs.

Western Cape: The Western Cape contributed 16.7% of the completions, reflecting lower engagement compared to Gauteng and KZN. The province's 2019 HIV prevalence is 6.76%, approximately half the national average⁸. This lower prevalence likely contributes to the reduced

focus on HIV education among HCPs, as healthcare professionals in the Western Cape may prioritise conditions more prevalent in their region.

Comparative Analysis of HIV-CPD vs Other CPDs

The digital platform offers a wide range of CPD activities, and a comparative analysis of engagement in the HIV-CPD versus “All Other CPDs” provides additional insights:

- **Gauteng:** Participation rates were comparable, with 59.0% for the HIV-CPD and 57.3% for other CPDs. This suggests a balanced approach to medical education in the province, where HCPs engage with diverse topics to address a wide range of patient needs.
 - **KwaZulu-Natal:** The HIV-CPD accounted for 24.3% of completions, compared to 20.4% for other CPDs. This indicates a stronger focus on HIV-related content among HCPs in KZN, reflecting the high prevalence of HIV in the province and the prioritisation of HIV education.
 - **Western Cape:** In contrast, participation in other CPDs (22.3%) exceeded that of the HIV-CPD (16.7%). This aligns with the province’s lower HIV prevalence and suggests that HCPs may focus on CPDs addressing other healthcare priorities more relevant to their patient demographics.
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Conclusion

The findings from the CPD activity "Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations" highlight the relevance of innovative monitoring techniques in advancing the global HIV response and aligning with the broader goals of the Sustainable Development Agenda. By leveraging data-informed approaches, the CPD initiative successfully engaged healthcare professionals (HCPs) across various provinces in South Africa, demonstrating the potential to enhance system-wide healthcare improvements through targeted educational interventions.

Key Highlights

The community-driven nature of the CPD activity was evident in its ability to attract diverse professional groups, including emergency medicine personnel, general practitioners, and community service doctors, who collectively accounted for the majority of completions. This inclusivity underscores the importance of tailoring CPD content to meet the unique needs of different healthcare providers, ensuring their preparedness to manage people living with HIV (PLWHIV).

Engagement metrics further revealed significant provincial variations, reflecting the intersection of regional HIV prevalence rates and the prioritisation of HIV education. Gauteng’s high participation rate highlighted the benefits of a well-connected healthcare infrastructure, while KwaZulu-Natal’s engagement underscored the importance of focused educational efforts in

areas with higher HIV burdens. Western Cape's lower participation mirrored its lower HIV prevalence, suggesting the need for region-specific strategies to address varied healthcare priorities.

SDG & HIV Education

This CPD activity directly supports Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages². By equipping HCPs with up-to-date knowledge and skills, the initiative contributes to the broader aim of reducing the HIV burden and improving clinical outcomes. The innovative monitoring and evaluation techniques applied in this study align with the SDG target to strengthen health systems and improve access to quality education for healthcare professionals².

In conclusion, the successful implementation of this CPD activity underscores the value of digital platforms in scaling impactful education and fostering professional development. As the healthcare landscape evolves, leveraging data-driven insights to tailor educational interventions will be pivotal in addressing global health challenges and achieving sustainable healthcare improvements.

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- **Background:** Indicate the purpose and objective of the research, the hypothesis that was tested, or a description of the problem being analysed or evaluated.
 - **Methods:** Describe the study period, setting and location, study design, study population, data collection and methods of analysis used.
 - **Results:** Present as clearly and in as much detail as possible the findings and/or outcomes of the study. Please disaggregate data by age and gender where possible and summarize any specific results.
 - **Conclusions:** Explain the significance of your study's findings and/or outcomes for HIV prevention, treatment, care and/or support and future implications of the results.
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Indicate the purpose and objective of the research, the hypothesis that was tested, or a description of the problem being analysed or evaluated.

Purpose and objective of the research

The purpose of this research was to evaluate the engagement and outcomes of a CPD activity, *"Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations,"* hosted on a digital medical platform. The aim was to highlight the effectiveness of data-driven monitoring techniques in enhancing education and supporting healthcare professionals (HCPs) in managing people living with HIV (PLWHIV).

Hypothesis Tested

The hypothesis tested was that data-informed monitoring techniques can significantly enhance the effectiveness and reach of CPD activities by engaging diverse healthcare professionals and aligning their educational needs with regional healthcare challenges, such as managing the HIV burden.

Description of the Problem Analysed

The study analysed the challenges in equipping healthcare professionals with up-to-date knowledge and skills necessary to manage people living with HIV (PLWHIV). These challenges include disparities in CPD engagement across different professional roles and provinces, and the need to align educational content with local healthcare priorities, particularly in regions with higher HIV prevalence. The research sought to demonstrate how digital CPD platforms can bridge these gaps and contribute to system-wide healthcare improvements.

Study Period:

The study was conducted over a six-month period from July 2024 to January 2025.

Setting and Location:

The research was based on data collected from a digital medical platform widely used by healthcare professionals (HCPs) in South Africa. The platform provided the *"Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations"* CPD activity.

Study Design:

This was a retrospective observational study aimed at evaluating user engagement, completion rates, and demographic participation trends in a CPD activity designed to improve HIV management education among HCPs.

Study Population:

The study included HCPs registered on the platform, who had successfully completed the HIV-CPD activity. Participants represented various medical professional roles

Data Collection:

Data was collected using Mixpanel, a digital analytics platform, to track user interactions with the CPD content. Metrics included:

- Completion rates
- Participant professional roles
- Engagement metrics (e.g., geographic distribution of participants)
- CPD ranking among other platform offerings

Additional analysis was conducted using Excel for data visualisation and percentage calculations. Aggregated and anonymised data ensured compliance with ethical standards.

Methods of Analysis:

Quantitative analysis was performed to assess completion rates, participation trends across provinces, and the demographic distribution of participants. Engagement metrics were compared to national HIV prevalence data to contextualise findings. Comparative analysis was also conducted to evaluate the performance of the HIV-CPD against other CPDs offered on the platform.

Statistical tools, including percentage calculations and basic trend analysis, were used to identify patterns and correlations between CPD engagement and regional healthcare priorities. Findings were aligned with the goals of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 to assess their broader implications for healthcare system strengthening.

The purpose of this research was to evaluate the engagement and outcomes of a CPD activity, "Advancing Towards HIV Elimination: Strategies, Challenges, and Innovations (HIV-CPD)". The aim was to highlight the effectiveness of data-driven monitoring techniques in enhancing education and supporting healthcare professionals (HCPs) in managing people living with HIV (PLWHIV).

The hypothesis was that data-informed monitoring techniques can significantly enhance the effectiveness and reach of CPD activities by engaging diverse HCPs and aligning their educational needs with regional healthcare challenges.

The study analysed the challenges in equipping HCPs with up-to-date knowledge and skills to manage PLWHIV. The research sought to demonstrate how digital CPD platforms can bridge gaps and contribute to system-wide healthcare improvements.

The study was conducted over a six-month period from July 2024 to January 2025. Data was collected from a digital medical platform widely used by HCPs in South Africa. This was a retrospective observational study, which included HCPs registered on the platform, who had successfully completed the HIV-CPD activity. Data was collected using Mixpanel, a digital analytics platform, to track user interactions with the CPD content. Additional analysis was conducted using excel for data visualisation and percentage calculations. Aggregated and anonymised data ensured compliance with ethical standards. Quantitative analysis was performed to assess completion rates, participation trends across provinces, and demographic distribution of participants.

A total of 4,359 HCPs successfully completed the CPD activity, representing 8.7% of the platform's active users. Emergency medicine personnel accounted for the largest share of completions (51.3%), followed by general practitioners (64% of the doctor cohort). Provincial engagement varied significantly, with Gauteng leading at 59% of completions, followed by KwaZulu-Natal (24.3%) and Western Cape (16.7%). The CPD ranked fifth among all platform offerings, highlighting strong interest in HIV-related education.

This CPD activity demonstrates the impact of community-driven and data-informed approaches in scaling education for HCPs. Provincial variations in engagement align with regional HIV prevalence, emphasising the need for tailored strategies to address healthcare priorities. The findings underscore the value of digital platforms in supporting SDG 3 by fostering professional development and strengthening health systems through innovative monitoring and evaluation techniques.

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